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Individualized prediction of the sound pressure at the eardrum for an earpiece with integrated receivers and microphones

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Future hearing systems and hearables will likely contain microphones and receivers in the ear canal. In order to predict the sound pressure at the eardrum in such a scenario, a one-dimensional electroacoustic model of a prototype open earpiece with integrated receivers and integrated microphones was developed. The model parameters were obtained in a training setup with well-defined loads at both sides of the earpiece. Subsequently, the prototype earpiece was put on individual subjects, and the model was then used to determine the acoustic impedance of the ear canal, which in turn was used to derive models of the individual ear canal and eardrum, by minimizing five types of cost functions and various parameters. Model predictions of the sound pressure at the individual eardrum were subsequently compared to probe-tube measurements in 12 human subjects. An analysis of the resulting errors led to identifying the best combination of cost function and associated parameters. This best combination resulted in an agreement between measurement and prediction of less than ± 3 dB and $\pm 20^\circ$ up to 3 kHz and less than ± 5 dB and $\pm 30^\circ$ up to 6–8 kHz, performing significantly better than both average transfer models and existing individualized predictions.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Acoustically open hearing aids that do not seal the ear canal are very popular, in particular, because they avoid the occlusion effect, i.e., the unwanted amplification of low-frequency components of one's own voice. The idea of using acoustically open fittings can also be extended to hearing systems for non-impaired users, sometimes referred to as "hearables." The acoustic leak that makes these systems open is usually provided by a so-called vent, an acoustic duct that connects the residual ear canal to the outside world.

More recently, it was proposed to equip the vent with electroacoustic transducers that could be used to actively influence the sound field in the ear canal, such that the original open-ear behavior in scenarios with external sound sources would be reproduced as closely as possible (Denk *et al.*, 2017a; Denk *et al.*, 2017b). The prototype system consisted of an open earpiece equipped with two miniature loudspeakers ("receivers" in hearing aid terminology) and three miniature microphones, one of which was located in the concha, whereas the other two were located in the vent. The idea was then that the concha microphone would sense the directional information of incoming sounds, and this signal should be filtered to obtain a certain target spectrum at the innermost microphone in the vent. As a first guess, it was assumed that the target spectrum should be equal to the spectrum of the concha microphone signal. Although this

approach relies on some rather crude assumptions (transfer function from the concha to the eardrum is independent of the position of the external sound source, transfer function from the innermost microphone to the eardrum is flat), it performed well in a listening test (Denk *et al.*, 2017a).

Alternatively, one could use electroacoustic models to better understand the acoustic transfer properties within the individual ear, both in the original open-ear case and in the case with the hearing system inserted. This could eventually be used to derive control strategies to achieve drum pressure equalization as well as active feedback, noise, and occlusion control.

In the current paper, we address the scenario where the hearing system is inserted, i.e., the problem of individually predicting the sound pressure created by the receivers at the eardrum, by using electroacoustic models of the hearing system and individual ear. More specifically, the transfer functions of the sound pressure at the eardrum relative to either the electrical voltage applied to a receiver or the sound pressure measured by the innermost microphone in the vent must be predicted individually.

Choosing the drum pressure as the relevant quantity to predict is motivated by (a) it providing a direct link to ear simulators and couplers and (b) because it was observed to be the most valid quantity to characterize the individual acoustical input to the auditory system in a study where the inter-individual standard deviation of pure-tone hearing thresholds in young normal-hearing subjects was investigated (Blau *et al.*, 2013).

The sound pressure at the eardrum can also be measured directly using probe-tube microphones. However, positioning a probe tube tip in the vicinity of the eardrum is a delicate

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task that does not lend itself to routine procedures and certainly not to adjusting the settings of mass-produced goods such as hearables. This has motivated several methods to individually predict the pressure at the eardrum from measurements made at remote points in the ear.

One group of methods that has been proposed is based on multiple measurements of the sound pressure along the ear canal axis (Farmer-Fedor and Rabbitt, 2002; Hudde, 1983). The measurement at precisely known positions in the ear canal is, however, practically challenging as well.

The drum pressure prediction can also be based on one measurement of the sound pressure (and sometimes also velocity) at the ear canal entrance. Most often, minima of the sound pressure are used to derive a transfer model from the entrance to the eardrum (Hudde *et al.*, 1999; Schmidt and Hudde, 2008; Souza *et al.*, 2014; Stevens *et al.*, 1987). Nonetheless, the success of these pressure-minima methods critically depends on the presence of well-pronounced minima, successfully distinguishing source spectrum minima, and well-estimated drum models (whose effects must also be separated from canal and/or source effects). These conditions can often be met with classical hearing aids, where quarter-wavelength minima around 4–6 kHz (i.e., in a frequency region where the eardrum can be assumed to be more or less rigid) are frequent, leading to pressure transfer functions that provide an amplification in the frequency region of the quarter-wavelength minimum.

Unfortunately, the specific design of the hearing system described in Denk *et al.* (2017b), which is investigated in the current paper, and presumably that of other hearables as well, poses new challenges.

First, the microphone positions are often more lateral than with typical hearing aids and second, the presence of transducers in the vent creates an acoustic duct that is partly obstructed. These modifications notably imply only weakly pronounced (i.e., strongly damped) quarter-wavelength dips, which are in addition shifted toward lower frequencies. Also, measured pressure transfer functions often exhibit attenuations (in the present study up to 15 dB less at the eardrum relative to the entrance) over broad frequency regions, which is often not accounted for using the abovementioned methods.

An alternative to pressure-minima-based methods are phase reflectance methods (Blau *et al.*, 2010; Hudde *et al.*, 1999; Rasetshwane and Neely, 2011; Sankowsky-Rothe *et al.*, 2015; Sankowsky-Rothe *et al.*, 2011), where the phase of the reflectance measured at the entrance to the ear canal is used to derive ear canal models. Referring to reflectance excludes source effects, but these methods still benefit from scenarios where drum effects do not interact with ear canal effects in the same frequency region.

In summary, many of the methods that have been proposed so far depend on favorable circumstances regarding the interaction of source, ear canal, and eardrum effects.

In an attempt toward a more robust approach that could be used for hearing systems such as the one described in Denk *et al.* (2017b), we propose to use an electroacoustic model (a) capable of correctly reproducing the individual interaction between source and ear canal, and (b) comprising

individual ear canal and drum models. This is based on earlier versions presented in Denk *et al.* (2017b) and Vogl *et al.* (2016), where preliminary results were shown. In the current paper, the electroacoustic model is explained in due detail with emphasis on investigating various choices for setting up ear canal and drum models from transfer function measurements between the receivers and microphones of the earpiece, and demonstrating the ability to individually predict the sound pressure at the eardrum in 24 ears.

II. METHODS

A. Model framework

The model framework to individually predict the sound pressure at the eardrum is shown in Fig. 1. The earpiece consists of a core element: an acrylic tube equipped with two receivers and two microphones and an earmold. The electroacoustic model uses lumped elements and two-ports, assuming one-dimensional sound propagation. The gray-shaded area relates to the core and is treated as independent of the individual subject, whereas both the radiation impedance and medially connected parts of the model are treated individually. In the following, each element of the model is described in detail.

B. Electroacoustic model of the core

1. Microphones and receivers

The microphones (Knowles Electronics GA38-30775-000, Itasca, IL) were modeled by their sensitivity $B = v/p$, where v is the microphone output voltage and p is the sound pressure. No further element is needed since the acoustic input impedance of the microphones is sufficiently high. The

FIG. 1. (Color online) Schematic of the prototype hearing system in an ear, with the electroacoustic model based on Vogl *et al.* (2016).

frequency-dependent, complex-valued function B was measured for each microphone by using a substitution method with a reference microphone (G.R.A.S. 40AF, Holte, Denmark) in quasi-free-field conditions [source: Genelec 8030A speaker (Iisalmi, Finland) at 50 cm distance, impulse responses 10 ms Hann-windowed to cut off room reflections].

The receivers (Knowles Electronics, lateral: FK-26768, medial: WBFK-30019, Itasca, IL) were modeled using the Norton equivalent circuit (see Fig. 2), i.e., by an ideal volume velocity source, characterized by its volume velocity per applied voltage, q_s/v_s , and an acoustic source impedance Z_s . The model parameters of the medial receiver are referred to as q_{s1}/v_{s1} and Z_{s1} , those of the lateral receiver as q_{s2}/v_{s2} and Z_{s2} . These complex-valued functions of frequency can be determined on the basis of measured transfer functions of the sound pressure in well-known acoustic loads, relative to the receiver voltage, p/v_s . Following the procedure outlined in [Blau et al. \(2010\)](#), four tubes of different length were used as loads. The sound pressure was measured at the ends of the tubes using a small microphone that effectively provided an acoustically rigid termination. The tubes themselves were characterized by two-port models whose chain transmission parameters t_{ij} were computed from their physical diameter and length using the tube models from [Benade \(1968\)](#). In order to compute the source parameters, the overdetermined system of equations

$$\begin{pmatrix} -t_{21, \text{tube 1}} & \frac{v_s}{p_{\text{tube 1}}} \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ -t_{21, \text{tube 4}} & \frac{v_s}{p_{\text{tube 4}}} \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} Z_s \\ \frac{q_s}{v_s} Z_s \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} t_{11, \text{tube 1}} \\ \vdots \\ t_{11, \text{tube 4}} \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

was solved for Z_s and $(q_s/v_s)Z_s$ at each frequency of interest using the pseudo-inverse; see also [Blau et al. \(2010\)](#).

Both the characterizations of the microphones and receivers were performed prior to assembling them into the core tube.

2. Core equipped with transducers

The air space in the core equipped with the transducers can be regarded as an acoustic duct with three different sections (see Fig. 1). Still assuming one-dimensional sound propagation, it was modeled by three two-ports representing the three duct sections (A_1, \dots, A_3 in Fig. 1), and a lossy acoustic mass (M_c and R_c) to account for the coupling to the residual ear canal. The two-ports, in turn, reflect acoustic transmission lines

FIG. 2. Circuit to measure the Norton equivalent parameters q_s/v_s and Z_s via known t_{ij} and measured p/v_s .

$$\begin{pmatrix} p_1 \\ q_1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \cosh(\gamma l) & Z_w \sinh(\gamma l) \\ \frac{1}{Z_w} \sinh(\gamma l) & \cosh(\gamma l) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} p_2 \\ q_2 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

with characteristic impedances Z_w and propagation constants γ . In contrast to the nonparametric models of the transducers, both Z_w and γ can be parametrized. To this end, the models proposed in [Benade \(1968\)](#) were used as a starting point. These models relate Z_w and γ to the radius r and length l of the duct section and the ambient temperature. It should, however, be noted that they assume perfectly rigid, cylindrical duct walls with no additional objects inside the cylinder. In order to account for the additional damping due to boundary layers around the objects in the duct (i.e., transducers, cables) and the non-smooth duct walls, the models were supplemented by multiplying the real part of the series impedance with a constant loss factor F_R . Thus, the model of the air space in the core contained 11 parameters (radii, lengths, and loss factors of the 3 duct sections as well as M_c and R_c). These parameters were eventually obtained from an optimization procedure in which the difference between measured and computed acoustic transfer functions was minimized; see [Vogl et al. \(2016\)](#).

To briefly summarize the procedure: The core was medially connected to an IEC 711 ear simulator (Holte, Denmark) and laterally flush-mount into a large baffle. This training setup was sufficiently similar to the intended use on a human subject, while providing well-defined acoustic loads at both ends of the core.

More specifically, the radiation impedance Z_{rad} characterizing the acoustic load at the lateral end was modeled as that of a piston in an infinite baffle having the radius r_3 of the outermost duct section

$$Z_{\text{rad}} = \frac{\rho c}{\pi r^2} \left(\frac{1}{2} (kr_3)^2 + j \frac{8}{3\pi} kr_3 \right), \quad (3)$$

where k is the wavenumber. The speed of sound c and the mass density ρ were computed by assuming an ambient air temperature of 20 °C (room temperature), i.e., $c = 343$ m/s and $\rho = 1.205$ kg/m³. The acoustic input impedance Z_{IEC711} of the IEC 711 simulator was determined experimentally using the method from [Blau et al. \(2010\)](#).¹

In the training setup, m transfer functions of core microphone voltages relative to receiver voltages (two microphones and two receivers, i.e., $m = 1, \dots, 4$) were measured. With the microphone sensitivities already determined (see Sec. II B 1), the measured transfer functions could be translated into transfer functions $H_{\text{meas}, m} = p/v_s$ of sound pressures at the microphones, relative to receiver voltages.

The same transfer functions were also computed from the electroacoustic models of the core and receivers and the terminating impedances. As an example, the computation of the transfer function of the sound pressure measured by the medial microphone p_1 relative to the voltage of the lateral receiver v_{s2} would include the following steps (refer to Fig. 1 with the individual ear canal being replaced by the IEC 711 ear simulator): first, all model elements lateral to the volume velocity source representing receiver 2 (Z_{s2} , A_3 , and Z_{rad})

were combined into one shunt impedance Z_{lat} , which in turn can be represented by a new two-port A_{lat} . Likewise, all model elements medial to microphone 1 ($j\omega M_c$, Z_{s2} , R_c , and Z_{IEC711}) were combined into another shunt impedance Z_{med} , which is represented by a new two-port A_{med} . Then, the overall transmission matrix A_{overall} could be computed by multiplying the transmission matrices of A_{lat} , A_2 , A_1 , and A_{med} (in that order), and the desired transfer function could eventually be obtained by

$$H_{\text{model,example}}(p) = \frac{p_1}{v_{s2}} = \frac{q_{s2}}{v_{s2}} \frac{1}{a_{21}(p)}, \quad (4)$$

with a_{21} being the (2,1)-element of A_{overall} and q_{s2}/v_{s2} is the voltage-related volume velocity of receiver 2 (known from Sec. II B 1). The dependency of a_{21} and hence $H_{\text{model,example}}$, on the 11 model parameters is indicated by putting a p (for “parameters”) into parentheses.

This procedure was repeated for the other three transfer functions, and the model parameters were then obtained by minimizing the squared difference between the computed and measured transfer functions,

$$J(p) = \sum_{m=1}^4 \sum_{f=400 \text{ Hz}}^{10 \text{ kHz}} (H_{\text{meas},m}(f) - H_{\text{model},m}(f,p))^2, \quad (5)$$

using a Nelder-Mead-simplex algorithm (Nelder and Mead, 1965). The initial values of the model parameters were estimated as follows: radii and lengths were estimated from the physical sizes of the duct sections; the loss factors F_R were initially set to one, and M_c and R_c were initially set to zero.

C. Core in the individual subject

1. Measuring the acoustic impedance at the entrance to the ear canal

Once the electroacoustic model of the core has been parametrized, the core can be inserted into an ear mold and put on an individual subject. Compared to the training setup described in Sec. II B 2, only the terminating acoustic loads represented by Z_{ec} and Z_{rad} are exchanged: the ear simulator by the individual ear canal and the large baffle by the individual pinna and head.

For the envisaged prediction of the sound transfer to the eardrum, we are mainly interested in the acoustic impedance Z_{ec} at the entrance to the ear canal, which we will use to construct individual ear canal models in Sec. II C 2. In order to determine Z_{ec} from measurements with the hearing system on the subject, the complete model lateral to the ear canal needs to be known, including the radiation impedance Z_{rad} . Fortunately, the resulting Z_{ec} is rather insensitive to changes in Z_{rad} , hence we continued to use the model from the training setup (piston in infinite baffle).

Then, Z_{ec} can be derived from one transfer function of the pressure measured with one of the microphones relative to the voltage applied to one of the receivers. Although either microphone could be used, it is advantageous to take the medial one (measuring p_1) because it is closer to the

impedance to be measured. Concerning the receiver, we used the lateral one ($s2$) for reasons explained in Sec. III B.

In order to illustrate how Z_{ec} is derived from the measurement of p_1/v_{s2} , a restructured version of the electroacoustic model from Fig. 1 is shown in Fig. 3: first, Z_{rad} , Z_{s2} , and A_3 are combined into one shunt impedance, which can be combined with A_1 and A_2 to a new two-port B , allowing one to formulate

$$q_1 = \frac{q_{s2} - b_{21}p_1}{b_{22}}, \quad (6)$$

with b_{21} and b_{22} being the elements of B ,

$$q_2 = q_1 - \frac{p_1 - j\omega M_c q_1}{Z_{s1}}, \quad (7)$$

and finally

$$Z_{\text{ec}} = \frac{p_1 - (j\omega M_c q_1 + R_c q_2)}{q_2}. \quad (8)$$

In practice, p_1/v_{s2} will be measured instead of p_1 , and likewise p_1 and all volume velocities in Eqs. (6)–(8) must be referred to v_{s2} . Since the division by v_{s2} occurs both in the numerator and denominator of Eq. (8), it can also be omitted for better readability. It follows that Z_{ec} can be computed from the measured transfer function p_1/v_{s2} and from the model parameters b_{ij} , Z_{s1} , M_c , R_c , and q_{s2}/v_{s2} .

The impedance can also be transformed into a reflectance R_{ec} if the effective area S_{eff} is known,

$$R_{\text{ec}} = \frac{Z_{\text{ec}} - Z_w}{Z_{\text{ec}} + Z_w} \quad \text{with} \quad Z_w = \frac{\rho c}{S_{\text{eff}}}, \quad (9)$$

where ρc is the characteristic (specific acoustic) impedance of air. For the medial end of the core, a circular effective area with a radius of 2 mm was assumed.

2. Ear canal and drum models

Because of the tube-like anatomy of the ear canal, the model of an acoustic transmission line may be a simple but sufficient approximation. To account for the variation in diameter along the canal, multiple two-ports E_1, \dots, E_n were chained (see Fig. 1). Each two-port represents a slice of the ear canal, modeled by an acoustic transmission line with

FIG. 3. (Color online) Equivalent circuit illustrating the derivation of Z_{ec} from the transfer function of the sound pressure measured by the medial core microphone (p_1), relative to the volume velocity of the lateral receiver (q_{s2}).

radius r_i and the fractional length l/n , with l being the total length of the canal. The optimum number n of slices required for the model is unknown: on the one hand, a larger n would allow for a finer approximation of the actual shape of the ear canal. On the other hand, a smaller n will result in a lower number of parameters to be estimated, which could make the model more robust. In this work, we used $n = 1, \dots, 7$ slices.

Similar to the work of Schmidt and Hudde (2008), a resistive load R_d located at the medial end of the ear canal was initially used to represent the load provided by the eardrum.

With l , R_d , and the n radii, $2+n$ parameters p have to be estimated in total for a given n . These parameters were estimated by minimizing different variants of cost functions: the first three were classical least squares cost functions

$$J(p) = \sum_{f=f_{\min}}^{f_{\max}} (X_{\text{meas}}(f) - X_{\text{model}}(f, p))^2, \quad (10)$$

where X was one of

- (1) the level of the ear canal impedance in dB, referred to as $Z_{\text{ec,level}}$,
- (2) the unwrapped phase of the ear canal impedance in radians, referred to as $Z_{\text{ec,phase}}$,
- (3) the unwrapped phase of the ear canal reflectance in radians, referred to as $R_{\text{ec,phase}}$.

The fourth version was a combination of the first and second and therefore named $Z_{\text{ec,level,phase}}$. More specifically, the costs from version one were added to the costs from version two weighted with ten, resulting in a cost balance of $1 \text{ dB} \hat{=} 1/\sqrt{10} \text{ rad} \hat{=} 18^\circ$.

The fifth version was based on the third: the squared difference of the unwrapped phase of the reflectance was in addition weighted with the absolute value of the measured reflectance, i.e.,

$$J(p) = \sum_{f=f_{\min}}^{f_{\max}} (\angle R_{\text{ec,meas}}(f) - \angle R_{\text{ec,model}}(f, p))^2 |R_{\text{ec,meas}}(f)|, \quad (11)$$

as suggested in Blau *et al.* (2010)—this is referred to as $R_{\text{ec,phase,weighted}}$.

Besides the cost function and the number of slices, other parameters may also potentially influence the estimation of the ear canal and drum models, in particular the lower and upper frequency limits in Eqs. (10) and (11) and whether the frequencies between the two limits are spaced linearly or logarithmically. For the lower frequency limit f_{\min} , two values were chosen: 1.2 kHz, which is just below the $\lambda/4$ dip of the measured Z_{ec} (see Fig. 5), and 3 kHz as used in earlier studies (see, e.g., Blau *et al.*, 2010). The upper frequency limit f_{\max} was set to values of 8, 10, 12, and 14 kHz, respectively. Both linear and logarithmic spacings were investigated as they balance the weighting of frequencies differently.

The Nelder-Mead-simplex algorithm was used again to minimize Eq. (10) or (11). In order to avoid unrealistic parameters, the following constraints were used in the

optimization: slice radii were bound to 1, ..., 6 mm, the total ear canal length to 8, ..., 30 mm, and the resistance R_d to 145, ..., 180 dB re Pa s/m³.

As with many optimization procedures, the results may depend on the chosen initial values of the parameters. Therefore, repeated trials were performed with randomly chosen initial values, which were uniformly distributed within the abovementioned bounds. The resulting parameters were then taken from the trial producing the lowest cost. It turned out that 100 trials were sufficient in the sense that further increasing the number of trials did not substantially lower the costs.

In summary, the search space for finding a set of parameters was spanned by (a) the number of slices n (7 levels), (b) the cost function (5 levels), (c) f_{\min} (2 levels), (d) f_{\max} (4 levels), and (e) the frequency spacing (2 levels), leading to 560 different combinations. Together with 100 trials, this resulted in 56 000 optimizations per experimental case. With the total number of cases being 48, resulting from 2 types of ear molds (individual versus generic; see Sec. III A) in two ears of 12 subjects, this amounted to about 2.7×10^6 optimizations.

In order to cope with this large number of computations, we substituted the transmission line models for the slices [Eq. (2)] by lumped-element T -circuits, as suggested, e.g., in Hudde *et al.* (1999); see Fig. 4. In addition to Hudde *et al.* (1999), we also included losses in the T -circuits (contained in R_a), which account for thermal and viscous effects at the slice walls. In contrast to the model of the core (Sec. II B 2), we did not use additional loss multipliers, such that the ear canal slice model depended on the slice radius and thickness only. The formulas relating R_a , M_a , and N_a to the slice radius r and length l were taken from Ballas *et al.* (2009),

$$R_a = R_{a0} \sqrt{\frac{\omega}{4\omega_g}} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{\frac{\omega}{\omega_g}}} \right) \quad \text{with} \quad R_{a0} = \frac{8\mu l}{\pi r^4}$$

$$\text{and} \quad \omega_g = \frac{8\mu}{\rho r^2}, \quad (12)$$

where μ is the dynamic viscosity and ρ is the ambient mass density of the air in the core,

$$M_a = M_{a0} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{\frac{\omega}{4\omega_g}}} \right) \quad \text{with} \quad M_{a0} = \frac{\rho l}{\pi r^2} \quad (13)$$

and

FIG. 4. Model of an ear canal slice using lumped elements (acoustic resistance R_a and reactance M_a and N_a).

$$N_a = \frac{\pi r^2 l}{\rho c^2}, \quad (14)$$

with c being the speed of sound of the air in the core. Assuming an ambient air temperature in the ear canal of 35 °C, the speed of sound is $c = 352$ m/s, the mass density $\rho = 1.145$ kg/m³, and the dynamic viscosity $\mu = 1.85 \times 10^{-5}$ kg/(m s). Compared to the exact formulation of Benade (1968), based on Bessel functions, the computation time is about 1/7, compared to the approximations given in Keefe (1984), the computation time is halved.

Once an ear canal model (including R_d) is found, there will be a residual difference between the acoustic input impedance $Z_{ec,model}$ of the model and the measured one. More specifically, the measured impedances $Z_{ec,meas}$ (see Fig. 5) often exhibit a certain ripple in the frequency region around 1, ..., 3 kHz, which is not present in the models. This is not at all surprising, since in that frequency region the ear canal input impedance is governed by the influence of the eardrum and we opted for an extremely simplistic eardrum model (purely resistive load) not capable of producing the observed ripple. In order to account for the observed mismatch between measurement and model, we therefore added a residual acoustic impedance

$$Z_{res} = \frac{e_{22}Z_{ec,meas} - e_{12}}{e_{11} - e_{21}Z_{ec,meas}} \quad (15)$$

in parallel to R_d (where the e_{ij} are the coefficients of the overall chain matrix containing E_1, \dots, E_n and R_d); also see Fig. 1.

At higher frequencies (> 2 kHz), the influence of the eardrum on the ear canal input impedance diminishes. In addition, in contrast to low frequencies where wave effects are not important, a mismatch occurring at the entrance of the ear canal can no longer be transformed to the end without changing the transmission characteristics of the model. As a pragmatic solution, a weighting function

$$w(f) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } f < 2 \text{ kHz} \\ 1 + 2 \times 10^{-6}(f - 2000 \text{ Hz})^2 & \text{for } f \geq 2 \text{ kHz,} \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

was multiplied to Z_{res} , effectively fading it out for frequencies beyond 2 kHz.

3. Prediction of the drum pressure

With all elements of the model of Fig. 1 determined, an appropriate predictor needs to be chosen. There are two options.

One option is to utilize the known volume velocity q_s of any of the two receivers. To this end, all model elements lateral to the receiver are combined into one shunt impedance, which in turn will be connected in parallel to the part of the model that is medial to the receiver, giving the overall chain matrix C . Then the transfer impedance can easily be computed

$$Z_{tr} = \frac{1}{c_{21}}, \quad (17)$$

with c_{21} being the element of C . The sound pressure at the eardrum is obtained from

$$p_{d,model} = q_s Z_{tr}. \quad (18)$$

Alternatively, one can use the measured pressure at the medial microphone (p_1). In this case, all elements medial to the position of the microphone measuring p_1 are combined into one two-port D , and the pressure transfer function p_d/p_1 can be computed from

$$\frac{p_{d,model}}{p_{1,model}} = \frac{1}{d_{11}} \quad (19)$$

with d_{11} being the (1,1) element of D and hence

$$p_{d,model} = \frac{p_{1,meas}}{d_{11}}. \quad (20)$$

The benefit of the first variant is that one may avoid difficulties associated with measuring p_1 at potentially unfavorable positions where near-field effects occur. Such near-field effects are expected to become relevant whenever the microphone is in the vicinity (a few millimeters) of discontinuities or sources (receivers), and the geometry of the setup on the individual subject is different from the one in the training setup, for instance, if the ear canal is strongly bent.

On the other hand, the first variant relies on all parts of the model, whereas the second variant uses only elements medial to the medial microphone, hence less potentially inaccurate model elements. Another argument in favor of the second variant is relying on the measured p_1 would allow for including external acoustic sources easily.

III. EVALUATION WITH HUMAN SUBJECTS

A. Subjects, setup, and preliminary checks

The aim of the evaluation with human subjects was to compare predicted and measured sound pressures at the

FIG. 5. Measured acoustic input impedance Z_{ec} of the residual ear canal for all 46 cases (in gray) and its mean value (in black).

eardrum under realistic conditions. Twelve subjects (ten male, two female, mean age: 28 yr) participated in the experiments. Each person declared themselves to have normal hearing and underwent a visual check via otoscopy prior to the experiments. All experimental procedures were approved by the Carl von Ossietzky University ethics committee.

Measurements were taken on both ears and with two sets of earmolds: one was an individual custom-made silicone mold, filling the *cavum conchae* and protruding approximately 8 mm beyond the first bend, similar to typical hearing aid fittings. Through a bore of 4 mm diameter, the core was pushed maximally into the mold such that its medial end remained in the earmold, approximately at the position of the first bend of the ear canal. It should be noted that between the medial end of the core and that of the earmold, a distance of approximately 8 mm remained, which could not further be reduced due to the mismatch between the geometry of the core (straight tube) and that of the ear canals.

The second mold was a generic silicone headphone tip (Bose StayHear plus, Friedrichsdorf, Germany), where one of the three available sizes was chosen such that the best possible fit for the particular subject could be obtained. The core was put into a small adapter, which allowed sufficient footing in the headphone tip. The medial end of the core ended with the tip, i.e., similar to the individual mold, it also ended approximately in the first bend of the ear canal.

To ensure quiet surrounding conditions, all measurements were performed in an anechoic room.

Custom-made microphone pre-amplifiers and amplifiers for the receivers were used together with an eight-channel soundcard (RME Multiface II, 44.1 kHz, 24 bit, Haimhausen, Germany) and a laptop computer. Recording and subsequent data analysis were carried out using custom software written in MATLAB (Natick, MA). All transfer functions were measured using a pseudo-reference-channel technique in which the reference (loop-back) channel was recorded only once, and the resulting correction was applied to every measurement afterward. This was possible since multiple measurements of the loop-back channel gave identical results.

Exponential swept sines generated according to Müller and Massarani (2001) were used as test signals. In order to achieve a good balance between sufficient signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and comfortable playback level, they were adequately pre-equalized using digital parametric equalizers.

The sound pressure at the eardrum was measured with a probe tube microphone (Primus, Auditdata, Taastrup, Denmark, same calibration as previously described in Sec. II B 1). The probe tube was gently inserted until the subject notified a sound or touch at the eardrum, at which point the tube was then pulled back by approximately 2 mm. Immediately afterward, the earpiece was inserted while the tube rested in the ear canal.

In previous studies, we used earmolds that had extra bores for the probe tubes. This was unfortunately not possible with the current earpiece simply because there was not enough space remaining. Hence, a certain risk of squeezing the tube or creating unwanted leakage remained and had to be dealt with.

In order to individually check for possible leakage caused by the probe tube, the pressure generated by the

medial core receiver was measured using the medial core microphone, both with the probe tube in place and without the probe tube. The expectation was that leakage should result in a loss at low frequencies (<300 Hz). However, no clear effects of the probe tube presence could be found. In some measurements, there was even higher pressure with the probe tube in the ear canal, indicating that the amount of sealing may rather depend on how tight the earmold was inserted, and not on whether a probe tube was present or not. Generally, differences between both conditions ranged within ± 3 dB for individual earmolds at <1.5 kHz, whereas for generic earmolds up to ± 5 dB were observed <2 kHz. In all cases, the absolute level differences decreased at higher frequencies.

Regarding a possible squeezing, simulations showed this would result in a broad-band level attenuation. In order to individually check for such problems, extra measurements with external loudspeakers (Genelec 6010, Iisalmi, Finland, 1 m distance) were performed with all subjects, once with the probe tube in place as described, and once with it pulled out and then measuring just in front of the earpiece. It should be expected that the differences between these two measurements vanish toward low frequencies (<100 Hz) due to the largely open venting of the earpiece, thus providing a means of individually checking for squeezing problems. Results confirmed the expectations, concluding that no problem due to squeezing existed for any of the subjects.

The above-described measurement with external loudspeaker excitation and the probe tube just in front of the earpiece also permits a verification of the core microphone sensitivities. This is again possible at low frequencies (<100 Hz), where the sound pressure can be expected to be the same at all microphone positions. It turned out that actual level differences were within ± 2.5 dB. Since earlier studies demonstrated that miniature electret microphones may change their sensitivity when inserted into ear canals at about these values (Sankowsky-Rothe *et al.*, 2015), we used the probe tube microphone as a reference and applied respective broadband corrections to the core microphones.

An inspection of the measured transfer function p_d/p_1 with either receiver as a source showed, in general, the anticipated convergence toward unity at low frequencies; see Fig. 16. However, 2 cases out of the 48 measurements were around $+4$ dB off and therefore regarded as incorrect measurements. These two cases were excluded from the subsequent analysis.

In order to ensure that subjects were not exposed to excessive levels, the individually measured sound pressure at the eardrum p_d was converted to free-field pressure (for frontal incidence), using individually measured real-ear unaided gain (REUG) functions. Subsequently, AF-weighted sound pressure levels $L_{AF}(t)$ were computed from the converted free-field pressure. Results confirmed that $L_{AF}(t)$ never exceeded 85 dB(A).

B. Measured impedances

The 46 measured acoustic impedances at the entrance to the ear canal are shown in Fig. 5, along with averages over impedance levels and unwrapped phase angles.

Prominent (albeit damped) quarter-wavelength dips can be observed around 2 kHz. At higher frequencies, the impedances exhibit $\lambda/2$ peaks around 6 kHz, followed by further dips and peaks.

Toward low frequencies (<1 kHz), the ear canal would be expected to act as a compliant load, i.e., the impedance magnitude should be inversely proportional to frequency and its phase should converge to -90° . In the measurements, this is rarely seen, indicating the presence of damped leaks in most measurements. These could, for instance, have occurred between the ear mold and ear canal. It must be stressed that the core itself was part of the source in these measurements, hence it is not responsible for the observed leaky behavior.

The inter-individual variability in impedance level is about 10–15 dB between 700 Hz and 5 kHz, and increases toward both lower and higher frequencies.

Because of its acoustically open architecture, the earpiece is not ideally suited as an impedance measurement system, and reliable results cannot be guaranteed at all frequencies. More specifically, problems arise at low frequencies (below around 500 Hz) and in the frequency region around 7–10 kHz, where the source impedance of the earpiece is typically lower than the input impedance of the ear canal; see Fig. 6. The small magnitude of the source impedance relative to the load makes p_1 (from which $Z_{ec,meas}$ is deduced) insensitive to changes of the load, and hence sensitive to measurement errors.

In order to avoid further computations based on erroneous impedances, affected frequency ranges were omitted from the cost functions [Eqs. (10) and (11)]. A simple criterion for which frequency range to omit was defined, based on the phase angle of the measured impedance: for purely passive systems, the phase angle of the impedance should be within $\pm 90^\circ$ —otherwise, the real part of the impedance

FIG. 6. Typical acoustic impedances: measured impedance at the entrance to the ear canal $Z_{ec,meas}$ (black), earpiece source impedance $Z_{earpiece}$ (red), modeled impedance of the ear canal without ($Z_{ec,model}$, blue) and with ($Z_{ec,model,incl,Z_{res}}$, dashed green) residual nonparametric impedance. Based on the criterion that the phase angle of the ear canal should be within $\pm 90^\circ$, the valid frequency range (which in this case was additionally limited to 10 kHz as upper frequency limit) is shown in gray.

would become negative, indicating an active “load.” For the computation of the ear canal models, we are only interested in the linear and passive transfer characteristics of the ear canals (and their terminating loads) and thus, only frequencies where the phase angle of the measured impedance was within $\pm 90^\circ$ were included in the cost functions and designated “valid frequency ranges,” as shown in Fig. 6. It turned out that the lateral of the two receivers provided slightly more valid ranges than the medial one, and therefore the impedances measured with that receiver were used.

Figure 6 further illustrates the effect of the residual nonparametric impedance Z_{res} , which was introduced in Sec. IIC2. When not included, $Z_{ec,model}$ (blue) only coarsely matches $Z_{ec,meas}$ (black), whereas including it makes it possible to account for the details below ≈ 2.5 kHz.

C. Comparison to probe tube measurements

In Fig. 7, an example of two model predictions of the sound pressure at the eardrum (one based on q_s , one based on p_1) is shown together with the probe tube measurement. The models and the measurement agree up to about 7–8 kHz and both models perform comparably well. Above 8 kHz, models and probe tube measurement diverge (with level differences of around 10 dB). This deviation may have been caused by inaccurate models or inaccurate probe tube measurements—the latter are known to become unreliable above about 7 kHz.

Recapitulating the large number of ear canal and drum model versions (560 different versions) \times 2 receivers \times two versions of predicting $p_{d,model}$ (based on q_s or p_1) for every of the 46 experimental cases, it is impossible to present *all* results in the detailed manner shown in Fig. 7 and hence some form of aggregation and/or selection is necessary.

First, we chose to represent the frequency-dependent deviations between model and probe tube measurement by a

FIG. 7. (Color online) Exemplary transfer functions of the sound pressure at the eardrum relative to the voltage at the lateral receiver, p_d/v_{s2} , for one of the 46 experimental cases: solid red, probe-tube measurement; dashed green, model based on q_s ; dotted blue, model based on p_1 . Both models were computed using $Z_{ec,level,phase}$ with linear frequency spacing from $f_{min} = 1.2$ kHz to $f_{max} = 10$ kHz and ear canal models with four slices.

single number, obtained from averaging the corresponding level differences over frequencies

$$\Delta L_{p_d} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \Delta L_{p_d,3\text{rdoct}}(k) \quad \text{with}$$

$$\Delta L_{p_d,3\text{rdoct}}(k) = \frac{1}{M(k)} \sum_{f_i \in B(k)} \left| 20 \lg \left(\left| \frac{p_{d,\text{model}}(f_i)}{p_{d,\text{meas}}(f_i)} \right| \right) \right|. \quad (21)$$

Here, k is the third octave band index, K is the total number of third octave bands, $B(k)$ is the frequency band corresponding to the k th third octave band, and $M(k)$ is the number of frequency bins within $B(k)$. Six third octave bands with mid frequencies from 2 to 6.3 kHz (i.e., frequencies from 1780 Hz to 7080 Hz) were considered. The high-frequency limit was motivated by the abovementioned reliability problems of probe-tube measurements above 7 kHz, the low-frequency limit by the observation that models and measurements agreed nearly perfectly below 1780 Hz in any case.

Analyzing ΔL_{p_d} revealed multiple interactions between all factors, both those considered in setting up the ear canal and drum models (cost function, lower and upper frequency limits, frequency spacing, number of slices) and those used for the prediction (receiver, prediction based on p_1 or q_s), and therefore no further averaging across these factors was performed as this would have smeared the effects.

Instead, selected subsets of the results are shown in the following. These subsets were selected such that the most important effects are represented, namely the influence of the cost function and that of the number of slices. Incidentally, cost function and the number of slices are also two of the factors with more than two levels (the upper frequency limit being the third), whose effects are shown in Fig. 8. As no averaging across factors is desired, the levels of the factors *not* being displayed must also be chosen—these were $f_{\min} = 1.2$ kHz, linear frequency spacing, lateral receiver, and q_s as predictor. The effects of these (less important) two-level factors will be analyzed later in terms of the difference to the combination shown in Fig. 8.

As already indicated and clearly visible in Fig. 8, the cost function has the largest effect on the resulting errors in terms of ΔL_{p_d} : Whereas $Z_{\text{ec,phase}}$ largely fails, both reflectance-based functions perform better, and the two impedance-level-based cost functions perform best. Out of the latter, $Z_{\text{ec,level,phase}}$ appears to have a slight advantage.

Concentrating on that cost function, a repeating pattern can be observed for the effect of the number of slices: increasing this number decreases the error for one to four slices, while for four slices and more, the error remains approximately constant. The conclusion is that a model with four slices should be sufficient when $Z_{\text{ec,level,phase}}$ is used. Also, still considering $Z_{\text{ec,level,phase}}$, the upper frequency limit f_{\max} does not seem to produce important effects.

FIG. 8. (Color online) Observed distribution of absolute level differences between modeled and measured p_d in terms of ΔL_{p_d} [Eq. (21)] for the 46 experimental cases as a function of the number of slices. Parameters are the cost function (rows) and the upper frequency limit (columns). Plus signs indicate medians. Remaining factors were $f_{\min} = 1.2$ kHz, linear frequency spacing, lateral receiver, $p_{d,\text{model}}$ based on q_s .

The combination of factor levels resulting in the lowest median of ΔL_{p_d} across the 46 experimental cases was: $Z_{\text{ecc,level,phase}}$ with linear frequency spacing from $f_{\text{min}} = 1.2$ kHz to $f_{\text{max}} = 10$ kHz, four slices, lateral receiver, and predictions based on q_s (central violin in the fourth row, second column in Fig. 8). This combination resulted in a median ΔL_{p_d} of 1.2 dB. In the following, the effects of the lower frequency limit, the frequency spacing, the receiver, and the predictor are analyzed by comparison to the just-mentioned best combination.

Changing the lower frequency limit from $f_{\text{min}} = 1.2$ kHz to $f_{\text{min}} = 3$ kHz worsens the predictions, indicated by positive differences of ΔL_{p_d} in Fig. 9. It must be noted, however, that the differences to the predictions with $f_{\text{min}} = 1.2$ kHz are rather small. This is a little surprising, given that with $f_{\text{min}} = 3$ kHz the first $\lambda/4$ dip around 2 kHz will not be included in the cost function for any experimental case. One possible explanation is that the residual impedance Z_{res} gives an optimal fit between $Z_{\text{ecc,model}}$ and $Z_{\text{ecc,meas}}$ below 2.5 kHz (see Fig. 6), with the consequence that in the 3 kHz-version the dip is also accounted for, which in turn improves the prediction of p_d .

The difference between logarithmic and linear frequency spacing is shown in Fig. 10. There does not seem to be any considerable effect at large, indicated by the medians being close to 0 dB. However, most of the distributions appear to be slightly skewed toward positive values, suggesting that logarithmic frequency spacing may yield considerably worse predictions in some cases. Apparently, the stronger weighting of high frequencies associated with linear spacing can be beneficial in such cases.

The comparison between the two receivers is shown in Fig. 11. In the top diagram, $p_{d,model}$ is based on q_s . No systematic differences can be seen, suggesting that the acoustic properties of the core and its lateral termination are sufficiently well represented by the model. If the predictions of the drum pressure for the two receivers are, however, compared with $p_{d,model}$ based on p_1 (bottom diagram), a systematic difference of approximately plus one dB is observed, i.e., the predictions get worse for the medial receiver. This systematic difference is nearly constant across the number of slices. We suspect that this behavior is caused by near-field effects. Two aspects might contribute: first, the medial receiver and microphone are positioned very close to each other (sound outlet/inlet within 2 mm) such that the medial microphone (measuring p_1) will sense the near field of the

FIG. 9. (Color online) Effects of the lower frequency limit f_{min} : distribution of $\Delta L_{p_d,3\text{kHz}} - \Delta L_{p_d,1.2\text{kHz}}$ for the 46 experimental cases, as a function of the number of slices. Plus signs indicate medians. Remaining factors were cost function $Z_{\text{ecc,level,phase}}$ with linear frequency spacing up to $f_{\text{max}} = 10$ kHz, lateral receiver, $p_{d,model}$ based on q_s .

FIG. 10. (Color online) Effects of the frequency spacing: distribution of $\Delta L_{p_d,\text{log}} - \Delta L_{p_d,\text{lin}}$ for the 46 experimental cases, as a function of the number of slices. Plus signs indicate medians. Remaining factors were cost function $Z_{\text{ecc,level,phase}}$ with frequencies from $f_{\text{min}} = 1.2$ kHz to $f_{\text{max}} = 10$ kHz, lateral receiver, $p_{d,model}$ based on q_s .

medial receiver. Second, on the subject both transducers are in the vicinity of the first ear canal bend, whereas the training setup (Sec. II B 2) is symmetric with respect to the core axis. Both aspects will likely interact and cause near-field effects not represented in the model. An additional hint that near-field effects may play a role comes from the observation (not shown here) that the measured transfer functions p_d/p_1 partly differed by up to ± 3 dB, depending on whether the medial or the lateral receiver was active, which is not consistent with the assumption of purely one-dimensional sound propagation in the core.

One can also look at the effect of whether $p_{d,model}$ is based on q_s or p_1 for the lateral receiver; see Fig. 12. For models with one or two slices, errors are larger if p_1 is used as a predictor, whereas no systematic differences can be seen for models with three or more slices. This is surprising because utilizing p_1 means that less potentially inaccurate parts of the core model are needed (only elements medial to the microphone measuring p_1 ; see Sec. II C 3), whereas

FIG. 11. (Color online) Effects of the receiver: distribution of $\Delta L_{p_d,\text{medial}} - \Delta L_{p_d,\text{lateral}}$ for the 46 experimental cases as a function of the number of slices. Plus signs indicate medians. (a) $p_{d,model}$ based on q_s , (b) $p_{d,model}$ based on p_1 . Remaining factors were cost function $Z_{\text{ecc,level,phase}}$ with linearly spaced frequencies from $f_{\text{min}} = 1.2$ kHz to $f_{\text{max}} = 10$ kHz.

FIG. 12. (Color online) Effects of the predictor: distribution of $\Delta L_{p_d, p_1} - \Delta L_{p_d, q_s}$ for the 46 experimental cases as a function of the number of slices. Plus signs indicate medians. Remaining factors were cost function $Z_{ec, level, phase}$ with linearly spaced frequencies from $f_{min} = 1.2$ kHz to $f_{max} = 10$ kHz, lateral receiver.

when q_s is used, all elements (medial and lateral to the microphone measuring p_1) must be included. A possible explanation is that the lateral elements may to some degree compensate for the errors caused by inappropriately low numbers of slices.

The abovementioned best combination of factor levels, resulting in the lowest median of ΔL_{p_d} ($= 1.2$ dB) across the 46 cases ($Z_{ec, level, phase}$ with linear frequency spacing from $f_{min} = 1.2$ kHz to $f_{max} = 10$ kHz, ear canal model with four slices, lateral receiver, $p_{d, model}$ based on q_s), is finally shown in more detail (i.e., as frequency-dependent transfer functions $p_{d, model}/p_{d, meas}$) in Fig. 13.

Below 300 Hz, deviations between model and probe-tube measurements are a consequence of poor SNRs in the measurements, caused by the low volume velocity of the source and low acoustic impedance load due to the venting. This results in a high-pass characteristic of $p_d/v_{s,2}$ with an edge frequency of 500–1000 Hz, depending on the individual ear; see Fig. 7.

From 200 Hz to 2 kHz, the deviations between model and measurement are within ± 2.5 dB/ ± 20 degrees, between 2 kHz and 7 kHz ± 5 dB/ ± 30 degrees with the exception of

FIG. 13. Transfer functions $p_{d, model}/p_{d, meas}$ of the 46 experimental cases in gray and 10%/90% percentiles in black for the best combination in terms of the lowest median of ΔL_{p_d} ($= 1.2$ dB). Factors were $Z_{ec, level, phase}$ with linear frequency spacing from $f_{min} = 1.2$ kHz to $f_{max} = 10$ kHz, ear canal model with four slices, lateral receiver and $p_{d, model}$ based on q_s .

four cases. Above that frequency, the deviations increase further. As already noted in the discussion of Fig. 7, one has to keep in mind that at such high frequencies, not only the model, but also the reference (probe-tube measurement) may become inaccurate. The percentiles shown in Fig. 13 also indicate that the distribution of deviations between model and measurement is approximately symmetric.

D. Derived ear canal and drum models

Using the optimization factors that lead to the best combination presented in Sec. III C (i.e., $Z_{ec, level, phase}$ with linear frequency spacing from $f_{min} = 1.2$ kHz to $f_{max} = 10$ kHz), the distributions of the resulting ear canal lengths and resistive loads are shown in Figs. 14 and 15.

A common feature of both the resulting ear canal lengths and resistive loads is that they tend to exhibit extreme distributions for low numbers of slices (up to three): either a concentration at the pre-defined bounds (ear canal lengths for one and three slices, resistive loads for two and three slices), or an almost uniform distribution, including many unrealistic values (ear canal lengths for two slices). Also, the distributions tend to change drastically if the number of slices changes.

This is no longer true for four and more slices, where the distributions remain very similar across different numbers of slices, indicating models less susceptible to changes in that parameter. Interestingly, this corresponds to the observation that prediction errors improve with increasing numbers of slices, and to settle with four and more slices; see Sec. III C.

Regarding the ear canal lengths, medians of around 25 mm result for four to seven slices, which corresponds well to the actual geometries. It must be kept in mind, however, that the objective was not to accurately estimate the ear canal geometry but rather the resulting acoustic input and transfer properties by using not too many parameters. In fact, it is possible to arrive at models with almost the same input impedance $Z_{ec, model}$ and also comparably good predictions of p_d with very different lengths (e.g., 15 and 30 mm)—simply because the remaining degrees of freedom of the model (notably radius functions and resistive loads) can step in.

Concerning the resistive loads R_d , values range within 145–160 dB with medians around 147 dB for four to seven

FIG. 14. (Color online) Distribution of the resulting ear canal lengths l for the 46 experimental cases as a function of the number of slices. Optimization parameters were $Z_{ec, level, phase}$ with linear frequency spacing from $f_{min} = 1.2$ kHz to $f_{max} = 10$ kHz.

FIG. 15. (Color online) Distribution of the resulting resistive loads R_d for the 46 experimental cases as a function of the number of slices. Optimization parameters were $Z_{ec,level,phase}$ with linear frequency spacing from $f_{min} = 1.2$ kHz to $f_{max} = 10$ kHz.

slices. In comparison, [Hudde and Engel \(1998\)](#) modeled the eardrum impedance as a frequency-dependent (complex) function, which can roughly be described by a minimum of 152 dB at 1 kHz and a plateau of 162 dB above 3 kHz. This is slightly higher than our findings, although the agreement is still acceptable, keeping in mind that in our model, *all* losses in the measured impedance Z_{ec} are primarily assigned to R_d .

IV. DISCUSSION

A. Comparison to predictions based on non-individualized transfer models

In order to assess the benefit of the proposed individualized prediction of the sound pressure at the eardrum, a first comparison was made to predictions that were based on a non-individualized transfer model of p_d/p_1 , together with individualized measurements of p_1 . One of the best-possible non-individual transfer models is obtained if the actually measured transfer functions p_d/p_1 for all but one experimental case are averaged and used to predict that specific experimental case. In Fig. 16, the measured transfer functions p_d/p_1 of the 46 experimental cases and their average values (of level and unwrapped phase, respectively) per frequency are shown and substantial differences between an individual and the average can be seen.

FIG. 16. Measured transfer functions p_d/p_1 for all 46 experimental cases (in gray) and their average values (of level and unwrapped phase) per frequency (in black).

In Fig. 17, the distribution of the resulting errors for the prediction using the non-individualized transfer models are shown, again in terms of ΔL_{p_d} at the rightmost position. The individualized predictions (center and left) result in significantly lower errors: using the best combination from Sec. III C, the median of ΔL_{p_d} is more than halved in comparison to the predictions with non-individualized transfer models (2.6 dB versus 1.2 dB, $p = 2.6 \times 10^{-9}$, $r = -0.88$, Wilcoxon signed-rank test).

In practice, one would try to avoid the rather costly measurement of p_d/p_1 with many subjects, and therefore even higher errors are to be expected with non-individualized predictions in general.

B. Comparison to other individualized prediction methods

Out of the many methods that have been proposed to individually predict the sound pressure of the eardrum (see also the Introduction), many use minima of the sound pressure spectrum measured at the entrance to the ear canal, which can provide information for setting up a transfer model to estimate p_d . For example, [Sankowsky-Rothe et al. \(2011\)](#) and [Souza et al. \(2014\)](#) obtained successful predictions in occluded ear scenarios when employing these methods.

However, the scenario treated in this paper is different: first, our data showed no clear minima (which also is reflected by the low quality factor of the $\lambda/4$ dips of Z_{ec} ; see Fig. 5). This is caused by the more lateral microphone positions and the partly obstructed, hence more damped, vent.

Second, in all studies cited, the pressure level at the eardrum was always larger than at the entrance, whereas for our data the opposite was observed in wide frequency ranges; see Fig. 16. As a consequence, it appears to be necessary to not only consider the minima (i.e. the zeros of Z_{ec}), but rather the full impedance function $Z_{ec}(f)$, except for the non-valid frequency regions discussed in Sec. III B. By doing so, one avoids important information of the ear canal and its termination being ignored. Also, by referring to Z_{ec} instead of

FIG. 17. (Color online) Distribution of ΔL_{p_d} for the 46 experimental cases. Plus signs indicate medians. (Left) individualized prediction using $Z_{ec,level,phase}$ with linear frequency spacing from $f_{min} = 1.2$ kHz to $f_{max} = 10$ kHz, ear canal model with four slices, lateral receiver, and $p_{d,model}$ based on q_s , (center) individualized prediction, using $R_{ec,phase,weighted}$ with linear frequency spacing from $f_{min} = 1.2$ kHz to $f_{max} = 8$ kHz, ear canal model with four slices, lateral receiver, and $p_{d,model}$ based on q_s , (right) prediction using non-individualized (average) transfer models p_d/p_1 .

to the pressure at the entrance, source properties are excluded automatically.

Regarding the methods based on the phase of the reflectance, our results show a clearly inferior performance compared to the impedance-based versions; see Fig. 8. In Fig. 17, this is again highlighted by picking the best combinations for both reflectance-based and impedance-based predictions (center and left). Using the best impedance-based predictions (median = 1.2 dB), the errors are significantly decreased in comparison to the best reflectance-based predictions (median = 1.9 dB, $p = 3.9 \times 10^{-6}$, $r = -0.68$, Wilcoxon signed-rank test). Nonetheless, the latter still perform significantly better than the non-individualized transfer models (median = 2.6 dB, $p = 0.02$, $r = -0.33$, Wilcoxon signed-rank test).

It is interesting to note that reflectance-based methods apparently worked better in other studies (Hudde *et al.*, 1999; Sankowsky-Rothe *et al.*, 2015; Sankowsky-Rothe *et al.*, 2011). We suspect that the discrepancy to the present study is again due to the “low” frequency of the $\lambda/4$ dips. In the studies cited above, these dips were in frequency regions where the termination of the ear canal by the eardrum can be assumed to be rigid (>3 kHz), which facilitates the estimation of separate models for the ear canal and eardrum, while still containing the important information of the $\lambda/4$ dip. In the present study, in contrast, $\lambda/4$ dips were in the frequency region where the eardrum impedance will influence Z_{ec} (or the derived R_{ec}), and hence a separation of ear canal and drum models is less obvious.

Another drawback of reflectance-based methods is that an area for calculating R_{ec} from the measured Z_{ec} needs to be known or estimated, providing additional potential for errors.

V. CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

In this paper, methods for the individualized prediction of the sound pressure at the eardrum generated by an open hearing device with integrated receivers and microphones were developed and validated by probe-tube measurements in 46 experimental cases.

Although the design of the hearing system in question bore similarities to classical vented hearing aids, existing methods that have been shown to work well for such hearing aids fail in the present case or produce inaccurate results. The failure of these methods can partly be explained by the shift of the characteristic $\lambda/4$ dip toward much lower frequencies and the increased damping in the present hearing system. This highlights the lacking robustness of such methods with respect to changes in the design of the hearing system and also to the choice of settings for the respective methods.

Being applied to the current hearing system only, the method proposed in this paper does not solve the problem of a high susceptibility to changes in design. However, it does provide a method to successfully predict the sound pressure at the eardrum for the current hearing system and, by having investigated a great number of conceivable model variants, it incorporates steps toward better robustness.

Future work should address the problem of susceptibility to design changes in order to be more generally applicable to the variety that can be expected for future hearing systems and hearables. The next step would be to extend the models to include external sources in open-ear scenarios such that these scenarios can eventually be emulated with the hearing system inserted.

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¹Please note that in that publication, Eq. (8) contains an error: b_{12} should be replaced by b_{21} in the relationship for c_1 .

- Ballas, R. G., Pfeifer, G., and Werthschützky, R. (2009). “Elektromechanische Systeme der Mikrotechnik und Mechatronik” (“Electromechanical systems of micro-technique and mechatronics” (Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg).
- Benade, A. H. (1968). “On the propagation of sound waves in a cylindrical conduit,” *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **44**(2), 616–623.
- Blau, M., Sankowsky, T., Roeske, P., Mojallal, H., Teschner, M., and Thiele, C. (2010). “Prediction of the sound pressure at the ear drum in occluded human cadaver ears,” *Acta Acust. united Acust.* **96**(3), 554–566.
- Blau, M., Sankowsky-Rothe, T., Köhler, S., and Schmidt, J.-H. (2013). “Using inter-individual standard deviation of hearing thresholds as a criterion to compare methods aimed at quantifying the acoustic input to the human auditory system in occluded ear scenarios,” in *Proceedings of the 21st International Congress on Acoustics*, Montreal, Quebec, Canada.
- Denk, F., Hiipakka, M., Kollmeier, B., and Ernst, S. M. A. (2017a). “An individualised acoustically transparent earpiece for hearing devices,” *Int. J. Audiol.* **57**(Suppl. 3), S62–S70.
- Denk, F., Vogl, S., Schepker, H., Kollmeier, B., Blau, M., and Doclo, S. (2017b). “The acoustically transparent hearing device: Towards integration of individualized sound equalization, electro-acoustic modeling and feedback cancellation,” in *Proc. 1st Int. Conference on Challenges in Hearing Assistive Technology (CHAT-17)*, August 19, 2017, Stockholm, Sweden, pp. 89–94.
- Farmer-Fedor, B. L., and Rabbitt, R. D. (2002). “Acoustic intensity, impedance and reflection coefficient in the human ear canal,” *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **112**(2), 600–620.
- Hudde, H. (1983). “Estimation of the area function of human ear canals by sound pressure measurements,” *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **73**(1), 24–31.
- Hudde, H., and Engel, A. (1998). “Measuring and modeling basic properties of the human ear and ear canal. Part III: Eardrum impedances, transfer functions and model calculations,” *Acta Acust.* **84**, 1091–1108.
- Hudde, H., Engel, A., and Lodwig, A. (1999). “Methods for estimating the sound pressure at the ear drum,” *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **106**(4), 1977–1992.
- Keefe, D. H. (1984). “Acoustical wave propagation in cylindrical ducts: Transmission line parameter approximations for isothermal and nonisothermal boundary conditions,” *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **75**(1), 58–62.
- Müller, S., and Massarani, P. (2001). “Transfer-function measurement with sweeps,” *J. Audio Eng. Soc.* **49**(6), 443–471.
- Nelder, J., and Mead, R. (1965). “A simplex method for function minimization,” *Comput. J.* **7**, 308–313.
- Rasetshwane, D. M., and Neely, S. T. (2011). “Inverse solution of ear-canal area function from reflectance,” *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **130**(6), 3873–3881.
- Sankowsky-Rothe, T., Blau, M., Köhler, S., and Stirnemann, A. (2015). “Individual equalization of hearing aids with integrated ear canal microphones,” *Acta Acust. united Acust.* **101**(3), 552–566.

- Sankowsky-Rothe, T., Blau, M., Rasumow, E., Mojallal, H., Teschner, M., and Thiele, C. (2011). "Prediction of the sound pressure at the ear drum in occluded human ears," *Acta Acust. united Acust.* **97**(4), 656–668.
- Schmidt, S., and Hudde, H. (2008). "Measurement of equal-loudness contours using eardrum pressure as reference signal," in *Proceedings of Acoustics'08*, Paris, France.
- Souza, N. N., Dhar, S., Neely, S. T., and Siegel, J. H. (2014). "Comparison of nine methods to estimate ear-canal stimulus levels," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **136**(4), 1768–1787.
- Stevens, K. N., Berkovitz, R., Kidd, G., and Green, D. M. (1987). "Calibration of ear canals for audiometry at high frequencies," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **81**(2), 470–484.
- Vogl, S., Sankowsky-Rothe, T., and Blau, M. (2016). "Elektroakustische Modellierung eines Ohrpassestücks mit integrierten Mikrofonen und Lautsprechern" ("Electroacoustic model of an earpiece with integrated microphones and receivers"), in *Fortschritte der Akustik (Proceedings of Acoustics)—DAGA 2016*, Aachen, Germany.